

STOCHASTIC SIMULATION OF THE CURE OF ADVANCED COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Polymer matrix composites (PMCs), Cure, Stochastic simulation, Statistics

ABSTRACT

A stochastic simulation methodology is developed to model and investigate the effects of cure kinetics, in plane fibre misalignment and boundary conditions uncertainty on the cure process of composite materials. Differential Scanning Calorimetry is used to characterise cure kinetics uncertainty of a commercial epoxy resin used in aerospace applications, whilst an in-house image analysis code is employed to characterise fibre misalignment of a $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF. In addition, an infusion set-up is used to quantify boundary conditions uncertainty related to tool temperature, ambient temperature and surface heat transfer coefficient. The resulting stochastic problem is addressed by developing models of variability for the different sources (kinetics, fibre orientation and boundary conditions) and coupling a cure simulation model with a Monte Carlo Scheme and an implementation of the Probabilistic Collocation method. It is shown that cure kinetics uncertainty can significantly affect the process outcome with a coefficient of variation in temperature overshoot of about 30%, whilst variations in surface heat transfer coefficient and tool temperature dominate variability in cure time introducing a coefficient of variation in cure time of 22%. Fibre misalignment can cause considerable variability in the process outcome with a coefficient of variation in maximum residual stress up to approximately 2% (standard deviation of 1 MPa) and qualitative and quantitative variations in final distortion of the cured part with the standard deviation in twist and corner angle reaching values of 0.4° and 0.05° respectively.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites manufacturing involves many sources of uncertainty associated with material properties and process parameters variability. These uncertainties can considerably influence the properties and the quality of the manufactured part, which in many cases can result in a considerable amount of scrap associated with significant cost and environmental implications. In addition, variability can significantly affect the efficiency of process cycles in terms of time and cost. The effect of material properties variability has been extensively investigated with a focus on reinforcement geometry. This type of variability is mainly associated with in-plane and out of plane fibre misalignment and can affect all the manufacturing steps.

Several experimental studies have indicated that in-plane fibre misalignment can be represented by a normally distributed random variable [1-5] and can present strong spatial autocorrelation over the textile. This can influence the forming process introducing considerable variability in defect generation [5]. In addition, fibre misalignment alongside nesting effects can introduce significant variability in permeability leading to considerable flow induced defects such as void formation and dry spots [6-8] which in turn can significantly deteriorate the performance of the manufactured part.

The issue of variability during the cure step has received limited attention so far in the literature. The cure process can be potentially affected by material properties variability related to fibre misalignment and resin behaviour uncertainty as well as environmental/boundary condition uncertainty. These effects can influence the risk of the occurrence of cure process defects such as resin degradation due to severe temperature overshoots, under-cure, pre-matrix cracks due to residual stress formation and

shape distortion degrading potentially the overall quality of composite parts. Very limited data and results exist concerning variability during the cure step, whilst the parameters introducing uncertainty into the cure process have not been explicitly characterised and evaluated. The effect of cure kinetics uncertainty and cure temperature uncertainty on cure time has been studied based on hypothesised levels of variability showing that cure temperature variations tend to dominate cure time variability [9]. Furthermore, consideration of variability in the optimisation of the cure time has shown that optimal cure time increases with increasing variability [10]. A characterisation and modelling approach that would take material properties and process parameters uncertainty into consideration explicitly is of crucial importance to allow quantification of process outcome variability within a stochastic simulation framework.

This study aims at the development of a stochastic simulation methodology to characterise and study the influence of cure kinetics, in plane fibre misalignment and boundary conditions uncertainty on the cure process outcome. A series of Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) tests were carried out to investigate cure kinetics uncertainty of a commercial epoxy resin used in aerospace applications, whilst an in-house image analysis code was used to characterise fibre misalignment of a $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF. An infusion set-up was used to characterize boundary conditions uncertainty related to tool temperature, ambient temperature and surface heat transfer coefficient using thermocouples (tool/ambient temperature) and heat flux sensors (heat transfer coefficient). The resulting stochastic problem is addressed by developing models of variability for the different sources of uncertainty and coupling a finite element based cure simulation model with a Monte Carlo Scheme (MC) and an implementation of the Probabilistic Collocation method (PCM). The two stochastic simulation methods are compared in terms of efficiency and accuracy. The focus was on studying the effect of cure kinetics uncertainty on temperature overshoot, the influence of fibre misalignment on residual stress formation and shape distortion and the combined effect of cure kinetics and boundary conditions uncertainty on cure time.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Cure simulation

A full thermo-mechanical cure simulation model is developed and implemented using the commercial finite element analysis solver MSC.MARC. The heat transfer problem is treated as a sub-case of the coupled solution. The model, which is based on the assumption of Cure Hardening Instantaneously Linear Elastic (CHILE) material [11, 12], is three dimensional and transient. The materials considered were Hexcel G1157 [13] pseudo unidirectional carbon fibre reinforcement and Hexcel RTM6 [14] epoxy resin. The material properties depend on both temperature and degree of cure and the material sub-models of cure kinetics, specific heat capacity, thermal conductivity, moduli, cure shrinkage and thermal expansion were implemented in user defined subroutines UCURE, USPCHT, ANKOND, HOOKLW, USHRINKAGE and ANEXP [15].

The cure kinetics model used in this study is a combination of an n^{th} order model and an autocatalytic model [17], while the specific heat capacity is calculated based on the rule of mixtures. A geometry-based model is applied to compute thermal conductivity [18]. A widely used micro-mechanics model [19] appropriate for unidirectional plies was chosen to model the mechanical properties of the composite as a function of the properties of the constituents. The simplicity of this model as well its direct parametrisation in terms of constituent properties makes it a suitable choice for the iterative use required in the context of stochastic simulation. Details concerning the equations and corresponding values of the material properties required for the different material sub-models can be found elsewhere [15].

2.2 Analysis of input parameters uncertainty

2.2.1 Cure kinetics

Differential Scanning Calorimetry tests were carried out at a heating rate of $1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ from 80°C to 240°C after equilibration at the initial temperature. Samples from four different batches were tested. All batches were within their shelf life at the time of testing. Tests were duplicated within each batch.

Integration of the heat flow versus time data using an iterative baseline [20] allows calculation of the degree of cure evolution and the corresponding reaction rate.

Estimation of cure kinetics parameters variability involved fitting of the cure kinetics model described in section 2.1 with each of the experimental curves [16]. The variability in experimental behaviour was attributed to certain parameters of cure kinetics as expressed by a phenomenological model and the corresponding stochastic object was developed. The procedure for characterization of cure kinetics uncertainty is detailed in [16].

2.2.2 Fibre misalignment

An in-house image analysis code described in detail in [5] developed to characterise fibre misalignment in woven textiles has been adapted to characterise local variations in unidirectional materials such as non-crimp fabrics (NCF). The image analysis code is based on Fast Fourier Transform and correlation analysis and its functionality is detailed in [21].

This methodology was applied to images of a 6k carbon fibre $\pm 45^\circ$ HTS carbon Hexcel NCF [13] with a chain knit stitch pattern. The areal density of this fabric is 534 g/m². A Sony camera was used to acquire digital images. The camera was mounted on a robotic head in order to control and record the exact position of each image. Seven hundred and forty-eight images were acquired from each side (upper/lower) of the $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF on a 34 \times 22 grid with 5 mm spacing. The size of the pixel array was 640 \times 480. The analysis of statistical properties was carried on the full dataset on a 5 \times 5 mm grid and additional datasets based on a coarser (10 \times 10 mm) and finer (2.5 \times 2.5 mm) grid which were produced using the original images. These additional datasets were utilised to verify that the analysis results do not depend on the grid size in terms of variance and autocorrelation structure. In addition, a series of 50 images were acquired at the same location and analysed to estimate the variance associated with the image acquisition and analysis methodology [21].

2.2.3 Boundary conditions

Investigation of boundary conditions uncertainty was carried out by a series of experiments using an infusion set-up. The experimental set-up comprised an ELKOM 8.4 KW electrical heating platen, a 10 mm thick aluminium tooling plate, a nylon N64PS-x VAC INNOVATION peel ply fabric, a nylon VAClease xR1.2 VAC INNOVATION vacuum bag, two K-type thermocouples and two RdF micro-foil heat flux sensors [22]. A 4.5 mm thick carbon fibre-epoxy flat panel fabricated by infusion was used to produce thermal conditions similar to those during the cure of a part. The matrix system of the panel was Hexcel RTM6, whilst the reinforcement was Hexcel AS7 12k carbon fibre [13] with an areal density of 268 g/m². The composite panel was placed on the tooling plate, covered with the peel ply and the vacuum bag and sealed before testing. Two heat flux sensors were mounted on the vacuum bag to measure natural air convection variability as well as its spatial dependence. A K-type thermocouple was placed on the tool to quantify tool temperature uncertainty and a second one away from the apparatus to measure ambient temperature variability. The temperature was equilibrated at 160 °C in all tests. A National Instruments LabVIEW in house code was used for data acquisition and the data were acquired with a frequency of 0.8 Hz. These experiments aimed at characterising the behaviour of stochastic parameters with time as well as across different experimental runs. The procedure followed to characterize boundary conditions uncertainty is detailed in [15].

2.3 Stochastic simulation

Due to the limited number of experimental data (Figure 1), the Kolmogorov-Smirnov goodness of fit test was carried out to investigate which statistical distribution is suitable to fit the three stochastic cure kinetics parameters. It was suggested that all variables can be represented by a normally distributed random variable with 99% level of confidence. The Cholesky decomposition was employed to model correlation between the three stochastic variables [16].

Fibre misalignment was modelled using a two-dimensional autoregressive stochastic process, the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck sheet (OU), which is a second order stationary Gaussian process [24-25]. The Cholesky decomposition was used to discretize the random field.

Surface heat transfer coefficient was modelled using random series of observations, while tool temperature and ambient temperature was modelled using a mean-reverting stochastic process the one-dimensional Ornstein-Uhlenbeck sheet (OU) [26] which is a variant of the stochastic process presented in section 3.3.1.2 appropriate for modelling variability with time dependence.

Two stochastic simulation approaches were developed based on conventional Monte Carlo (MC) and the Probabilistic Collocation Method (PCM), respectively [15]. The two stochastic simulation models were coupled with the finite element based cure simulation model. The Monte Carlo method presents a robust but usually computationally expensive solution, whilst the collocation method can offer a efficient solution with comparable accuracy. The Monte Carlo scheme was implemented in all case studies whereas PCM was used to investigate the effect of cure kinetics uncertainty on temperature overshoot as well as the combined effect of surface heat transfer coefficient and tool temperature variability on cure time.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Experimental results

3.1.1 Cure kinetics

Fig. 1 illustrates the results expressed as reaction rate versus temperature for the eight tests carried out. All curves have the same qualitative characteristics with a peak at intermediate temperatures and a shoulder towards the end of the reaction. The main peak of the reaction tends to be slightly asymmetric and ends with a plateau at a low reaction rate. This is followed by a drop to negligible reaction at very high temperatures. The repeatability within the same batch is very high with curves being almost identical. In particular, the absolute differences between curves of the same batch for values of degree of cure of 20%, 40%, 60% and 80% varied from $8E-06$ to $2E-05$ [1/s], which is more than one order higher than the values of cure reaction rate obtained by the experiments. This shows that the experimental and signal analysis method induces negligible variations to the results. In contrast, significant variability can be observed in the comparison between batches. This variability is manifested in the maximum reaction rate, the position of the maximum, the temperature at which the reaction starts and the temperature of the high temperature shoulder.

Following the procedure summarized in section 2.2.1 it was found that the main sources of uncertainty in the experimental results are the variability in the initial degree of cure α_0 , activation energy E_2 and reaction order m presenting a coefficient of variation of 19, 1 and 7 %, respectively [16].

Fig. 1 Evolution of reaction rate as a function of temperature during dynamic cure at 1°C/min. Letters denote the different batches of resin and numbers different samples within the same batch.

3.1.3 Fibre misalignment

The experimental results show that both sides of the fabric present identical statistical behaviour in terms of probability distribution and autocorrelation structure. The variability in tow orientation is considerable reaching a standard deviation of 1.2°. The standard deviation obtained for the set of images from a single location is 0.1°, indicating that the experimental and image analysis method introduces negligible variations to the results. No correlation was observed between the tow orientations of the two sides. The experimental results suggested that tow orientation can be represented by a normally distributed variable.

The autocorrelation structure (Figure 2) of the orientation of the tows was investigated in order to estimate the spatial dependence of variability. It can be observed that fibre misalignment of the $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF exhibits anisotropic spatial autocorrelation with the major direction of autocorrelation coinciding with the direction of the stitch (0°). This reflects the fact that the majority of variability is introduced during the stitching process of non-crimp fabrics. The autocorrelation in this direction decays towards a negligible plateau value at about 100 mm. In the $\pm 25^\circ$ directions the autocorrelation reaches a plateau at about 40 mm, whilst autocorrelation at $\pm 50^\circ$ and $\pm 75^\circ$ shows a faster decay, reaching zero at approximately 25 mm. It can be observed that the autocorrelation in opposite directions is very similar, suggesting that the autocorrelation structure is quadrant symmetric. The spatial cross-correlation between the orientations of the tows of the two sides of the fabric was found to be negligible [21].

Fig. 2 Directional autocorrelation of tow orientation of $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF - 0° refers to the orientation of the non-structural stitch.

3.1.4 Boundary conditions

Figures 3, 4 and 5 present the experimental results of tool temperature, ambient temperature and surface heat transfer evolution for the ten tests. A variable level across the different experimental runs is observed for all three parameters. This implies that in addition to time variations there is a dependence of the underlying level of each parameter across the different runs. In terms of time dependence the tool temperature presents a periodic trend and short term variability as shown in Figure 3. The periodic trend is more pronounced and is governed by the temperature controller, whilst short term variability is due to random variations. The periodic features presented here correspond to the tooling set up of this study. The ambient temperature measurements exhibit a non-periodic long term trend and short term variability (Figure 4). The differences between the results obtained by the two heat flux sensors placed at different location on the vacuum bags were negligible implying that there is no spatial dependence of the surface heat transfer variability. The surface heat transfer coefficient shows short term variability and a variable level [15].

Fig. 3 Tool temperature as a function of time.

Fig. 4 Ambient temperature as a function of time.

Fig. 5 Surface heat transfer coefficient as a function of time.

3.2 Stochastic simulation results

3.2.1 Influence of cure kinetics uncertainty on temperature overshoot

The cure of a 30 mm thick carbon fibre- epoxy laminate fabricated by infusion was modelled by coupling the two stochastic simulation schemes with the finite element based cure simulation model. The standard cure profile for the epoxy system of this study (Hexcel RTM6) was used. The lay-up

sequence of the laminate was $[0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_{25}$. The initial temperature was set at 15°C and was applied to all the nodes of the model. Figure 6 presents the probability distribution of temperature overshoot for the two stochastic simulation schemes. Satisfactory convergence behaviour was obtained for the first and second statistical moments of temperature overshoot after 2000 Monte Carlo iterations for both stochastic simulation schemes. A very good agreement is achieved between MC and the collocation method. The results suggest that temperature overshoot presents a coefficient of variation of 31 %. Examination of the probability distribution of temperature overshoot shown indicates that temperature overshoot can be considered a normally distributed random variable.

Fig. 6 Probability distribution of temperature overshoot.

3.2.2 Influence of fibre misalignment on residual stress formation and shape distortion

The cure of an angle shaped carbon fibre- epoxy subcomponent was modelled by coupling a Monte Carlo scheme with the finite element cure simulation model. The bracket is 2 mm thick, with two arms of 100 mm in length whilst the inner radius is 3 mm. The width of the component is 40 mm. The standard cure profile for the epoxy system of this study (Hexcel RTM6) was used. Three different lay-up sequences were investigated: a cross-ply $[0/90/90/0]_s$, a bias-ply $[45/-45/-45/45]_s$ and a quasi-isotropic (QI) $[0/45/-45/90]_s$ laminate; here all orientations are with respect to the long axis of the component. Figure 7 and 8 present the probability distribution of maximum residual stress and twist angle for the three lay-ups. The results suggest that stress presents a coefficient of variation of 2.3, 1.4 and 1.2 % (standard deviation of 1.29, 0.76 and 0.75 MPa), for the cross ply, bias ply and quasi-isotropic laminate respectively. Examination of the probability distribution shown in Figure 7 indicates that maximum stress can be considered a normally distributed random variable. The mean value of stress is higher than the corresponding nominal value resulting from the deterministic simulation in all three case studies. This is due to the fact that the distribution of residual stresses depends on the local properties of the laminate and deviations of the nominal fibre orientation at a local level generate higher levels of stresses locally.

Examination of the deterministic model results illustrated in Figure 8 suggest that the quasi-isotropic laminate presents a small but finite twist with the bias-ply and cross-ply laminate showing negligible twist. In the case of the deterministic model the perfect cross ply laminate presents no twist due to the fact that no twisting moment is generated. In the case of the perfect bias-ply lay-up twisting is counteracted by the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers, whereas in the case of the perfect quasi-isotropic lay-up the twisting moment is not resisted sufficiently at the bias direction showing the highest levels of twist. This explains the deterministic model results for the maximum longitudinal stress shown in Figure 7; higher

levels of distortion result in higher stress levels. The results suggested that the twist presents a standard deviation of 0.4° , 0.01° and 0.08° , for the cross ply, bias ply and quasi-isotropic laminate respectively. This is attributed to the differences in stiffness in the bias direction in each lay-up. Therefore, the cross ply laminate is the most susceptible to local deviations from the perfect nominal orientations presenting the highest variability in twist given that no fibres are aligned in the $\pm 45^\circ$. In addition, the different levels of variability in twist can explain the differences in standard deviation of maximum stress between the three lay-ups as shown in Figure 7. In addition, it was indicated that the spring-in angle exhibits small variation with a standard deviation not higher than 0.05° for all lay-ups.

Fig. 7 Probability distribution of maximum longitudinal residual stress.

Fig. 8 Probability distribution of twist angle.

3.2.3 Influence of cure kinetics and boundary conditions uncertainty on cure time

The cure of a 3.6 mm thick carbon fibre- epoxy laminate fabricated by infusion was modelled using the stochastic simulation approach developed in this study [15]. The lay-up sequence of the laminate was $[0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_3$. The standard cure profile of Hexcel RTM6 was used. Five different cases were investigated using Monte Carlo taking into account: (i) cure kinetics and boundary conditions uncertainty, (ii) cure kinetics uncertainty only, (iii) ambient temperature variability, (iv) tool temperature variability and (v) surface heat transfer coefficient variability.

Figure 9 illustrates the probability distribution of cure time taking into account cure kinetics and boundary conditions uncertainty. The results suggest that cure time presents a coefficient of variation of 21.8 %, 1.2%, 1.1%, 12% and 17.4% (standard deviation of 47.4, 2.6, 2.3, 25.7 and 37.4 min) for the five cases. Examination of the probability distribution shown in Figure 9 indicates that cure time can be considered a normally distributed random variable. These findings show that the surface heat transfer coefficient and tool temperature dominates cure time variability. Therefore, for the given case stochastic simulation can be limited to these two factors when efficiency is important, e.g. in iterative use. In addition, utilisation of a surrogate model based on PCM can reduce execution times further. This scenario was tested here with the simulation of surface heat transfer and tool temperature variability propagation using both MC and PCM (Figure 10). The results suggested that both stochastic simulation schemes are able to capture the combined effect of surface heat transfer coefficient and tool temperature variability in cure time accurately, with MC offering an accurate but computationally expensive solution and PCM an efficient solution with comparable accuracy [15].

Fig. 9 Probability distribution of cure time for cure kinetics and boundary conditions uncertainty.

Fig. 10 Probability distribution of cure time for surface heat transfer coefficient and tool temperature uncertainty.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The methodologies developed in this work allow the quantification of the influence of variability on the cure process outcome. The experimental results show that high specification materials involve uncertainty, which in turn can introduce significant variability to the process outcome. In addition, boundary conditions can present significant variability affecting the process outcome. The stochastic simulation results suggest that cure kinetics uncertainty can introduce significant variability to the cure process with a coefficient of variation in temperature overshoot of about 30 %, with potential implications in the amount of scrap during the manufacturing process of composite materials. In addition, fibre misalignment in the order of 1 ° can affect residual stress formation and shape distortion during the cure with the maximum residual stress presenting a coefficient of variation up to about 2%, whilst the average level of stress being higher than that for the nominal fibre orientations, with potential implications in the performance of manufactured parts. Although the variability in spring-in angle is small in absolute terms, considerable qualitative variations in shape can be induced by the presence of fibre geometrical variability. Furthermore, it was indicated that surface heat transfer coefficient and tool temperature dominate cure time variability introducing a coefficient of variation of about 22%, with considerable implications in cost associated with process duration and part quality.

The Monte Carlo scheme is capable of predicting uncertainty propagation with high accuracy and it is not limited by the dimension of the stochastic problem; however it is computationally expensive. Therefore, is capable to address every stochastic problem in the context of composites manufacturing. On the contrary, the collocation method can offer an efficient alternative to Monte Carlo for a small number of stochastic variables, implying that it is limited to address specific sub-problems of the manufacturing process (for example cure kinetics uncertainty) and not the full stochastic problem, where several sources of variability are in action. Therefore, the collocation method is not indicated to address stochastic problems involving stochastic fields such as fibre misalignment, due to the fact that in most cases a large number of stochastic variables is required to represent a stochastic field accurately.

The findings presented here bring light to the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of material properties and process parameters variability and uncovered the relationship between this variability and the curing process outcome. This enhances the knowledge of the curing process and brings new awareness in terms of decision making. In addition, this work provided greater insight regarding the sources of variability in composites cure, which in turn can be used in order to eliminate this variability. The methodologies developed in this study can serve as a starting point for incorporation of variability in process design/optimisation to minimise the probability of process induced defects such as resin degradation due to temperature overshoot variations, under-cure, matrix cracks due to variations in residual stresses generation and shape distortion while using a process design as efficient as possible in terms of duration and energy consumption.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council [grant number: EP/IO33513/1], through the EPSRC Centre for Innovative Manufacturing in Composites (CIMComp).

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